

RETHINKING FINTECH ADOPTION MODELS THROUGH A GENDER-BASED PERSPECTIVE

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Abstract

Purpose. Financial technologies (Fintech) are a rapidly growing area of research. As Fintech continues to expand worldwide, targeted strategies that take into account differences in adoption factors are becoming essential. This research examines variations in the adoption and use of digital financial technologies based on gender. The study of gender disparities in the adoption of banking Fintech raises broader questions about digital literacy, financial independence, multiple responsibilities placed on women, literacy, and access to technology, particularly in developing countries.

Methods. This paper provides an overview of theoretical models of technology adoption in the field of Fintech. Based on the identification of six the most widely used theoretical models of technology adoption, we conducted a study of the variables that make up these models in order to determine the presence or absence of the gender variable.

Results. Analysis of the six main models (Technology Acceptance Model, Unified Theory of Acceptance and Use of Technology, Unified Theory of Acceptance and Use of Technology 2, Task Technology Fit, Initial Trust Model and Information System Success Model) reveals that gender is present in two out of six original models. It does not appear as an external variable directly affecting usage, but is most often a moderating variable added to the initial designs in order to moderate the effects on intention or usage.

Implications. The findings of this study show that Fintech adoption is not a neutral process, but occurs within a sociocultural context in which gender roles shape digital behaviors. It also opens up theoretical perspectives by calling for a move beyond the traditionally moderating role of gender to consider it as a central explanatory variable adapted to cultural contexts. In terms of national strategies, explicitly integrating a gender perspective into digital transformation, educational programs, and access to technological infrastructure would promote equitable technological inclusion and help reduce disparities in access to and use of Fintech solutions.

Keywords: Fintech, adoption, theoretical models, gender, digital inclusion.